

MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TEACHING OF ECONOMICS

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Abstract. *This article covers the role of modern pedagogical technologies in the development of Education. Also, the article is based on the fact that in the process of training on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies and pedagogical technologies in the teaching of Economics and management, it is necessary to pass using modern technical means, computers, multimedia complexes with video computers, in addition, students will have independent knowledge, be able to develop conclusions and suggestions on the analysis,*

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Any new pedagogical technology is based on educational principles that shape the new content of Education. The implementation of the activity makes it possible to organize it, to make a decision on cooperation between the teacher and the student of active subjects of the educational process, to perfectly master theoretical and practical knowledge on the subject (or the basics of the sciences). It also includes tasks such as developing student activity and interest in science during the course of the session, in addition to creating conditions for the assimilation of educational material, taking into account the personal and collaborative activities of students with the teacher. We know that the priority tasks of the Ministry of innovative development, such as “promotion of research and innovation activities, creation of effective mechanisms for practical implementation of scientific and innovative achievements” and ensuring the development of innovations in the educational system from the main areas of activity of the Ministry of innovative development, are established in the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The effect of the reforms carried out in our country today depends, first of all, on the expansion of the ranks of young personnel with high morale, independent thinking, capable of taking responsibility for the fate and prospects of our homeland.

If we look at the 2nd stage of the national program of Personnel Training, we are setting the task of introducing new pedagogical technologies in education and using them wisely. This puts huge responsible tasks on the responsibility of all educators.

So what should be the modern teacher first of all? it is necessary that we find the answer to the question: After independence, this problem became the focus of many scientists, even parents. But research and research on this problem continues today. For the convenience of teachers, methodical and educational manuals, textbooks began to be created that could meet modern, current requirements. Global changes, the day-to-day development of Science and technology and information and communication technologies require the teacher of the 21st century to have pedagogical skills, sharp will, pedagogical-psychological knowledge, deep knowledge of his own science and political literacy, a wide and thoughtful range of thinking.

This is done through the use of improving teaching, the widespread implementation of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process, as well as the implementation of the use of multimedia capabilities. Such technology encourages students in the course of classes to think independently, to operate freely.

And the term pedagogical technology is based on a new approach to the educational process. Currently, pedagogical technologies are called in relation to the creation of computer and information technologies of education and their use in the course of the lesson. Pedagogical technologies this means a radical assimilation of the educational process, the introduction of methods and methods, technical means, forms of teaching into the educational process, taking into account the uniqueness of each student.

Pedagogical technology in education is to educate students with interest and achieve complete mastery of knowledge, to provide an opportunity for students to express their opinion. The most basic requirement when conducting a lesson in the process of pedagogical technology is the provision of knowledge based on the student's life experience, previously acquired knowledge and interests.

So the future of each society is determined by the extent to which the educational system is developed, which is an integral part of it. The work of reforming the educational system in our country, introducing advanced pedagogical technologies of developed countries into it, organizing education with the absorption of our national values, carrying out this process carefully and efficiently has risen to the level of state policy today, which is able to continue without deviations in the strategic path of strengthening the Muslim economy. So the main goal of reforming the system of continuing education in our country is to train competitive specialists in every aspect of the perfect person and mature qualified.

It is known to us that with the emergence of mankind, it is necessary that they meet their needs so that they can grow, develop, produce the blessings necessary for their survival, and that humans can live and work. Previously, economic activity consisted of household, by the present time it consists of large private, collective, Joint-Stock Companies, State Farms, financial and banking system, various inter-farm, Interstate associations, corporations, associations, joint ventures, inter-state relations.

Currently, the resources necessary for production are limited: natural resources, funds, means of production, labor. It is a fundamental issue of the economy to use these limited economic resources effectively to meet the ever-growing needs of the population, to find ways to rationalize resources and products. To meet these requirements, it is important that the student has in-depth knowledge and skills in the science of Economics and management.

Like other disciplines, the science of Economics and management has its own subject, theory and methods of research. The subject determines what this science deals with, what area it belongs to, while the theory determines the laws of the occurrence of processes and phenomena that occur in the field. It is necessary to develop a system of various means and methods of studying how the scientific and practical activities of people are carried out based on the theory of research methods.

The science of Economics and management gives students a special place in assessing the essence and types of all types of enterprises, their role and importance in the economy, external and internal factors and ways of their analysis, and the results of all socio-economic reforms in our republic, as well as the level of selection of goals and objectives of industrial development.

From the above, the essence of the economics and management course is studied through the following topics:

subject and tasks of the science of the moment;

Enterprise – a market entity of an independent economic entity of the enterprise of the year; the main and working capital of the enterprise and production capacity of the enterprise of the year; innovative and investment activities of the enterprise of the year;

enterprise labor resources and labor remuneration system; cost of production (work, Service), profit and profitability of the enterprise; business plan of the enterprise;

organizational structures of management; CEC management methods, leadership and its culture;

stages of development and adoption of the management decision of the office; strategic planning of the office and its implementation;

methods of production and personnel management of the office; competence, responsibility, control and efficiency in the management of the office.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that currently there are a lot of knowledge, the acquisition of which is radically changing on the basis of the requirements of time and space, large changes are taking place not only in the sum of modern necessary knowledge, but also in the methods of learning new knowledge. Since a perfect person and a mature qualified specialist are formed in the process of specially organized pedagogical activity, the role of teachers in this process is incomparable. All the knowledge received by students is important in the training of qualified personnel capable of effectively conducting their work activities in various branches of enterprises. Providing the population with quality products - even in increasing the efficiency of enterprises-is one of the most important main tasks of the national economy. To carry out this task, it is necessary to expand production, carry out innovative and investment activities, carry out effective management, effectively use financial resources, store raw materials, form an assessment, management methods and make the right decisions. Together with increasing the amount of products of the organization of all types of enterprise, it is possible to rapidly develop the economy, provide all sectors of its industry with raw materials.

REFERENCES

1. Azizxodjayeva N .N. Pedagogik texnologiya va pedagogik mahorat (darslik). - T. 2006 y.
2. Ishmuxammedov P., Abdukodirov A., Pardaev A. Tarbiyada innovatsion texnologiyalar. (o‘quv qo‘llanma). T., 2010.
1. 3.Interfaol metodlar: mohiyati va qo‘llanilishi / Metodik qo‘llanma. Tuzuvchilar: D.Ro‘zieva, M.Usmonboeva, Z.Holiqova. – Toshkent: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU nashriyoti, 2013.
3. Pedagogik texnologiyalar. Tuzuvchilar: Sh.S.Shodmonova va b. – T.: “Fan vatexnologiya”, 2011.
4. Gulova, M.N. Innovatsion pedagogic texnologiyalar: darslik. DPT muassasalari uchun qo‘llanma / MN Gulova, 4-nashr, qayta ko‘rib chiqilgan. – M .: IT akademiyasi, 2013.